

Phacoemulsification Transition: A Novice's Guide to Techniques, Tips, and Pitfalls in Sub-Saharan Africa

Edak EZEANOSIKE¹, Sayema SHARIEF², Saudat G HABIB³, Kabir BELLO²

¹Department of Ophthalmology, Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital Abakaliki/ Ebonyi State University Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. ²Makkah Specialist Eye Hospital Kano, Albasar International Foundation Kano, Nigeria. ³Department of Ophthalmology, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, College of Health Sciences Bayero University Kano/ Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital Kano.

ABSTRACT

Background: Phacoemulsification has revolutionized cataract surgery globally, becoming the gold standard due to its superior outcomes and rapid recovery. In Sub-Saharan Africa, the evolution of cataract surgery has progressed from traditional techniques like couching and intracapsular cataract extraction (ICCE), to extracapsular cataract extraction (ECCE), manual small incision cataract surgery (MSICS), and now to phacoemulsification. However, adopting phacoemulsification in the region is met with unique challenges, including resource constraints, limited access to training, and patient-related factors. **Objective:** This guide aims to equip novice surgeons with practical skills, techniques, and insights necessary for mastering phacoemulsification, addressing the complexities, common pitfalls, and key strategies for successful transition within Sub-Saharan Africa. **Methodology:** The authors documented their structured training journey in transitioning from MSICS to phacoemulsification. The guide details the challenges faced, training modalities, and strategies for overcoming obstacles to achieve competence in phacoemulsification. **Results:** Key pathways to proficiency are outlined, covering preoperative planning, step-by-step surgical techniques, intraoperative complication management, and postoperative care. The guide emphasizes the importance of structured training programs, effective mentorship, continuous learning, and ethical practice for skill development. **Conclusion:** Phacoemulsification in Sub-Saharan Africa offers both challenges and opportunities for novice surgeons. With structured training, mentorship, and a commitment to continuous learning, surgeons can improve outcomes, reduce complications, and promote wider adoption of this advanced technique, ultimately enhancing patient care.

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*Correspondence

Edak Ezeanosike
Department of Ophthalmology,
Alex Ekwueme Federal University
Teaching Hospital Abakaliki/
Ebonyi State University Abakaliki,
Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Email: edakspeaksout@gmail.com
Tel: +2348060377988.

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INTRODUCTION

Cataracts remain the leading cause of blindness globally, with a significant burden in Sub-Saharan Africa due to limited access to surgical services.¹ The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that over 50% of blindness in this region is attributable to cataracts.² Cataract surgery is reported as the single most cost-effective surgical intervention in health care.³ The burden of cataract is most prevalent in low- and middle-income countries, where limited access to timely surgical services results in substantial preventable blindness. In sub-Saharan Africa, the high prevalence is further driven by factors such as increased exposure to ultraviolet radiation, limited awareness of the availability and benefits of cataract surgery, inadequate access to treatment facilities, gender-related barriers, and financial constraints.^{1,4,5}

As global populations rise and life expectancy continues to increase, the demand for effective cataract surgery is projected to increase, making proficiency in cataract surgical techniques a critical requirement for ophthalmologists. Phacoemulsification offers an important solution to the cataract burden in Sub-Saharan Africa by providing superior surgical precision, quicker visual rehabilitation, and better long-term outcomes. While Manual Small Incision Cataract Surgery (MSICS) remains a cost-effective option with proven value in resource-limited settings, phacoemulsification represents the aspirational standard of care and is increasingly feasible as technology becomes more affordable and training opportunities expand across the region.

However, phacoemulsification presents a steep learning curve, requiring trainees to master fine surgical skills and anatomical knowledge for safe and effective practice. Kelman in 1967 first described the technique of phacoemulsification using ultrasound to emulsify and remove the cataractous lens through a small incision, allowing implantation of an artificial intraocular

lens (IOL) with faster recovery time.⁶ Over the decades, phacoemulsification has evolved with advancements in machine technology, surgical instruments, and IOL designs, making it safer, more effective, and the preferred technique for modern cataract surgery. This steep learning curve demands deep mastery of ocular anatomy and physiology, proficiency with the use of fine surgical instruments, excellent eye-hand-foot coordination and dexterity within the delicate and limited space of the anterior chamber.

Many contend that manual small incision cataract surgery (MSICS) is the preferred technique for cataract removal in sub-Saharan Africa, achieving outcomes comparable to those of phacoemulsification. Manual small incision cataract surgery has the advantage of reduced costs, suitability for surgery in resource-constrained settings, and the ability to manage dense cataracts that might be challenging with phacoemulsification.⁷

Although phacoemulsification offers faster recovery and less postoperative astigmatism, MSICS is widely used in low-income regions and achieves outcomes comparable to phacoemulsification.

Arguing this, in Sub-Saharan Africa, the diverse sociocultural environment, enriched by education, financial capacity, and the availability of information on the internet, ensures that enlightened patients are well-informed about advanced surgical techniques and consistently seek superior care. There is poor knowledge of phacoemulsification technique in Africa but this trend continues to change over time.⁸ The contemporary ophthalmic surgeon must therefore be prepared to match demand with appropriate services. Hence, we see a rapid transition of surgeons from MSICS to phacoemulsification to cater for this niche of patients. Some hospitals in sub-Saharan Africa offer phacoemulsification as the first line treatment for cataracts in up to 90% of their patients.⁹ With the availability of more affordable and cost-effective phacoemulsification machines, more hospitals in sub-Saharan Africa

will continue to drift in this direction. Studies show MSICS and phacoemulsification yield similar outcomes, but phacoemulsification causes less astigmatism and is preferred in western countries. Thus, Cook *et al.* recommend African surgeons transition to phacoemulsification.^{10,11}

This paper provides a guide for trainees to master phacoemulsification, covering essential skills, equipment handling, and complication management to ensure safe, competent practice and optimal patient outcomes.

UNDERSTANDING

PHACOEMULSIFICATION

Components of the Phacoemulsification Machine

The phacoemulsification machine has several essential components:

The handpiece: This is a critical and sensitive part of the machine which uses ultrasonic vibrations to disintegrate the lens for removal. It comprises the handpiece itself and a detachable tip which is covered by a silicon sleeve. The tip has orifices on its side through which irrigation fluid flows out. The silicon sleeve spreads this fluid on the tip to cool it and minimise thermal damage to surrounding ocular tissues (Figure 1). The tip may be straight or bent, and the tip bevel may range from 0 - 60 degrees, offering better occlusion at 0 degrees but faster sculpting at 60 degrees.

The handpiece houses a hollow ultrasonic probe often made from titanium or stainless steel, housing piezoelectric crystals that convert electrical energy into ultrasonic waves. It oscillates at very high frequencies to pulverise the cataractous lens into minute fragments. The handpiece also houses the irrigation portal that maintains the anterior chamber depth and ensures tip cooling, as well as a vacuum-driven aspiration system to extract the emulsified lens material and excess fluid from the anterior chamber. The handpiece is connected to the machine via tubings for irrigation, aspiration, and power supply, facilitating precise control over parameters such

as flow rate, vacuum pressure, and ultrasound intensity.

Figure 1. A:Phaco Handpiece and tubings
B:Phaco Tip

The Irrigation and Aspiration (I&A) System: This plays a crucial role in maintaining anterior chamber stability during cataract surgery by balancing fluid inflow and outflow, preserving intraocular pressure (IOP) and the structural integrity of the anterior chamber (AC) and cornea. Irrigation delivers sterile fluid into the anterior chamber via the handpiece or a separate cannula. Its main function is to maintain chamber shape, prevent collapse, and flush debris and emulsified lens fragments. Fluid delivery is strictly controlled by either using gravity or a pressurised

pump system, dynamically adjusting flow rates to prevent IOP fluctuations and ensure constant AC stability.

Concurrently, the aspiration system eliminates emulsified lens material, excess fluid, and debris using vacuum. Vacuum pressure and flow rate are controlled using foot pedals, allowing precise real-time adjustments as surgery progresses. The aspiration system works in tandem with irrigation to maintain fluid equilibrium, ensuring a stable anterior chamber throughout the operation. This delicate fluid balance is only possible if the port size precludes excessive leakage from around the probes.

Contemporary phacoemulsification machines feature advanced capabilities to enhance I&A system performance. These include real-time adjustments, occlusion detection, and surge suppression technology to prevent sudden IOP drops caused by blockage of the aspiration pathway. Anterior chamber maintenance by the I&A system reduces complications such as endothelial cell damage or posterior capsule rupture and provides a clear surgical field for enhanced surgical outcomes (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Irrigation and Aspiration (I&A) Probes

The foot pedal: This functions in three distinct stages: irrigation, aspiration, and emulsification. The initial stage involves gentle pressure to

activate irrigation, introducing a balanced salt solution (BSS) or its substitute into the anterior chamber. This maintains the chamber's stability and shape, ensuring a clear, well-hydrated surgical site and preventing AC collapse. As the surgeon increases pressure, the pedal moves to the aspiration mode, initiating the removal of fluid, emulsified lens fragments, and debris from the AC. The pedal allows for seamless adjustment of vacuum pressure and aspiration flow, enabling precise management of outflow whilst maintaining anterior chamber stability.

The final stage, activated by further increase in pedal pressure, initiates emulsification. Here, ultrasonic energy is delivered via the handpiece tip to fragment the cataractous lens. During this phase, the surgeon simultaneously controls ultrasound power, irrigation fluid inflow, and aspiration vacuum energy, using the foot pedal. This integrated control facilitates efficient lens removal whilst minimising trauma to surrounding ocular tissues (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The Foot Pedal

The Control Console: This is a comprehensive interface that serves as the central hub for monitoring and adjusting settings during cataract surgery. It ensures a seamless procedure by allowing surgeons to customise and fine-tune machine parameters to meet the specific requirements of each surgical phase. The screen displays the essential settings, such as irrigation flow rate, aspiration vacuum, and ultrasonic

power. These parameters are dynamically modified to align with the surgical demands at various stages, including lens emulsification, fragment removal, and anterior chamber maintenance. Real-time feedback on the display enables surgeons to monitor performance and make appropriate adjustments as required.

Modern consoles feature user-friendly interfaces, often incorporating touchscreens or buttons, facilitating quick and intuitive alterations to machine settings. Advanced systems may offer pre-programmed modes tailored to various cataract densities or surgical techniques and surgeon peculiarities and preferences, thus streamlining the process. The assistant saves the peculiar preferences of each surgeon, obviating the need for repeated manual adjustments.

Beyond displaying settings, the console integrates crucial safety features, such as occlusion detection, surge suppression, and alarms, which alert surgeons to potential complications. These features enhance patient safety by enabling prompt intervention when anomalies occur.

This synchrony of all components of the phacoemulsification machine – irrigation, aspiration, and ultrasonic energy – ensures precision and efficiency during surgery. By providing real-time data and straightforward control, it serves as an indispensable tool for optimising surgical outcomes and enhancing the overall surgical experience. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. The Console

The Vacuum Pump System: This plays a vital role in maintaining anterior chamber stability by controlling the removal of fluid and lens fragments during cataract surgery. This system generates the necessary suction to aspirate emulsified material whilst ensuring a stable and secure surgical environment. Two main types of pumps are employed: peristaltic and Venturi, each suited to different levels of surgical expertise and preferences.

Peristaltic Pumps

Peristaltic pumps are particularly advantageous for novice surgeons due to their precise and controlled aspiration capabilities. These pumps utilise compressible flexible tubing squeezed by a series of rollers, creating a controlled fluid flow. The roller speed determines the flow rate, offering surgeons predictable and adjustable suction. This regulated approach reduces the risk of sudden pressure fluctuations, facilitating chamber stability maintenance, especially for less experienced surgeons. The ability to fine-tune the flow enables a safer and more gradual removal of lens fragments at the cost of speed.

Venturi Pumps

Conversely, Venturi pumps are designed for seasoned surgeons who favour swifter and more efficient procedures. These pumps function by generating vacuum power through differential air pressures, producing a robust suction force. This mechanism allows for rapid lens fragment removal, considerably reducing procedure duration. However, Venturi pumps demand greater skill and precision, as their high vacuum power can result in abrupt pressure changes if not carefully managed. They are particularly suitable for dense cataracts and cases where speed and efficiency are paramount.

Each machine brand has a specific pump type inbuilt and therefore utility would depend on availability.

PHACODYNAMICS

A thorough understanding of the components of the phacoemulsification system is essential; however, mastery of the principles of phacodynamics is equally critical for achieving safe and effective cataract extraction.

Ultrasound power is produced by piezoelectric crystals in the handpiece, causing high-frequency vibrations at the phaco tip. The stroke length and frequency influence emulsification efficiency and heat production, with a balance between “jackhammer” impact and cavitation effects.

The **foot pedal** as earlier described, has three settings for irrigation, aspiration, and ultrasound control. Proper use optimizes flow and vacuum, balancing attraction and repulsion at the tip. Surgeons adjust parameters like duty cycle, aspiration rate, and vacuum for efficiency and safety, selecting either fixed or variable settings. Tailoring these based on nucleus density helps minimize tissue damage while achieving effective emulsification. The different positions of the foot pedal are associated with different sounds which should be learned by the trainee.

The two main factors in phacodynamics are **fluidics** (balance of inflow and outflow) and **ultrasound power**. Proper fluid settings maintain a stable anterior chamber by balancing inflow (regulated by bottle height) and outflow (controlled by the aspiration flow rate). The settings are individualised to the pace and requirements of the operating surgeon. Low inflow risks chamber collapse, while high inflow can stress ocular structures with risk of endothelial cell damage and posterior capsule rupture. Fluid pumps, either peristaltic or Venturi, manage this flow, with low-compliance tubing and other settings reducing the risk of chamber surge.¹¹ Followability is the attraction of the lens fragments towards the phaco tip which depends on the vacuum generated. When outflow exceeds inflow, surge (sudden shallowing of the anterior chamber) occurs. Low compliance

tubing, decreased flow and vacuum, micro pulse phaco, venting, and variable rise time decrease surge.^{12,13} The ultrasound power is generated by the piezoelectric crystals moving at high frequency with maximum efficiency at 35-45KHz, lower being inefficient, and higher generating heat.¹³ Occludability (tendency of the tip to get occluded thus building up the vacuum) depends on the size and angle of the phaco tip.

Playing with the machine: For effective emulsification, a balance of attraction and repulsion forces at the phaco tip are required. The aspiration flow rate pulls the material towards the tip, and the ultrasonic power of the probe pushes the material away. Vacuum keeps the fragments at the tip.

These settings can be optimized by the surgeon based on preferences. Low flow settings slow down the events while high flow speeds them up. Low vacuum is useful during sculpting, during which high power is applied to a hard or large nucleus. The duty cycle refers to the time period where ultrasonic energy is actively in use. High duty cycles result in heat generation and increased risk of endothelial damage. The denser the cataract, the higher the duty cycle required to emulsify it. Adjustment of the duty cycle, power modulation with pulsed, burst and hyperpulsed phaco power optimizes safety and efficiency.

All parameters (vacuum, aspiration, ultrasound) during phacoemulsification surgery can be selected as fixed (preset value activated when foot pedal enters appropriate position) or variable (settings increase linearly through continued excursion of the foot pedal in given position). Generally, energy damage to ocular tissues is minimized by choosing the most efficient nucleus disassembly technique and choosing settings that efficiently utilize power.

Indications And Contraindications for Phacoemulsification Surgery

While generally suitable for various cataracts, contraindications include low endothelial cell count, corneal opacities, shallow anterior chambers, zonular weakness, advanced glaucoma, and dense cataracts. Patients on medications like Tamsulosin that results in a floppy iris, may face complications, and adaptations may be required for advanced cataracts.⁹

Preoperative Considerations

Patient Selection and Assessment: Careful patient selection optimizes surgical outcomes. Attention must be given to visual or functional impairment, ocular health, systemic conditions (e.g., diabetes, hypertension), and psychosocial factors. Novice surgeons are advised to avoid cases with mild visual impairment early in their training to allow for patient appreciation of visual improvement after the procedure. Softer cataracts are also more suited for the trainee than denser cataracts

Preoperative Investigations and Optimization: B scan ultrasonography, Intraocular pressure documentation, Biometry, keratometry, and OCT aid in surgical planning, while systemic health assessments stabilize conditions like diabetes and hypertension. In high-risk patients, an endothelial cell count may be necessary, and infections should be controlled to prevent postoperative complications.

Patient Counselling and Informed Consent

Effective communication is fundamental for managing expectations, alleviating preoperative anxiety, and ensuring truly informed decision-making. Counselling should provide a clear explanation of the surgical procedure, anticipated benefits, potential risks and complications, alternatives to surgery, and realistic postoperative outcomes – including the possibility of residual spectacle dependence or

the need for further procedures. The informed-consent process should be documented in writing and discussed in person, allowing adequate time for the patient to ask questions and for the surgeon to confirm the patient's understanding and voluntary agreement to proceed.

Equipment Preparation and Operating Room Setup:

Ensure all instruments are sterilized, organized, and phacoemulsification machine settings calibrated to the case. Confirm the correct IOL is available and sterile, with backups on hand. Prepare emergency equipment and conduct a team briefing to review accuracy of patient details and special considerations, optimizing safety and surgical outcomes. A non-foldable lens should always be handy in case there is a need to convert to MSICS.

LEARNING PHACOEMULSIFICATION

Learning phacoemulsification is often challenging for beginners because it requires the integration of multiple discrete skills and techniques, as well as mastery of the stepwise sequence of the procedure. Surgical proficiency is commonly judged by both technical competence and the achievement of consistently good visual outcomes.

The learning process typically includes:

Understanding Ocular Anatomy and Physiology:

A solid grasp of the anatomical structures involved – including the cornea, lens, zonules, and vitreous body – together with knowledge of ocular physiology, is fundamental for anticipating and managing potential intraoperative challenges.¹⁴

Familiarity with Instruments and Consumables:

Trainees should become acquainted with all instruments and consumable materials used in the procedure. Observing experienced surgeons during live or video-assisted surgery helps build familiarity. Hands-on practice in proper handling

and controlled movement of each instrument is essential for developing safe and efficient technique.¹⁴

Instruments and consumables: Get acquainted with the items used for the procedure as you watch your trainer. Practice the handling and movements with each instrument.

Eye-Hand-Foot Coordination

Precise coordination and fine motor skills are essential for performing delicate manoeuvres within the confined space of the anterior chamber during intraocular surgery. In phacoemulsification, this challenge is compounded by the integration of the foot pedal as a critical control element. Developing the ability to synchronise hand movements with foot-pedal positions—and to correlate these positions with the auditory feedback provided by the phacoemulsification machine—is fundamental to safe and efficient surgery.

Historically, training in Manual Small-Incision Cataract Surgery (MSICS) and earlier extracapsular techniques has benefited from the use of mammalian enucleated eyes, which provide an accessible and cost-effective model that closely simulates human ocular tissue.⁽¹⁵⁾ However, because prion proteins—the causative agents of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease—can accumulate in the ocular tissues of infected humans and certain animals, and are highly resistant to standard sterilization, there is a theoretical risk of prion transmission if phacoemulsification or other reusable ophthalmic equipment is shared between animal eyes (used for wet-lab practice) and human patients without effective prion decontamination. This concern underpins current recommendations against using human phacoemulsification machines on animal eyes for training purposes.^{16,17}

In many resource-limited settings, the lack of dedicated wet-lab machines or simulators implies that trainees must initially develop eye-hand-foot

coordination in live surgical cases—posing an additional challenge. As an improvised training step, after MSICS procedures, the extracted nucleus may be placed in an intraocular lens (IOL) pack partially filled with balanced salt solution and resealed to mimic a closed chamber. The trainee can then practise emulsifying the nucleus with the phacoemulsification handpiece to gain an early appreciation of emulsification dynamics and the response of the machine to varying pedal pressures.

Technical Skills

Competence in phacoemulsification requires familiarity with specialized instruments and the phacoemulsification system itself. Key steps include constructing a self-sealing corneal or scleral incision, creating a continuous curvilinear capsulorrhexis of appropriate size, hydrodissecting the nucleus from the cortex, cracking and fragmenting the nucleus, emulsifying the fragments with ultrasound energy, aspirating residual cortical material, and securely implanting the intraocular lens. Evidence shows that hands-on training using wet labs and surgical simulators significantly enhances technical performance and improves surgical outcomes.¹⁸ Moreover, understanding the principles of the machine's fluidics, power and vacuum modulation, and their effects on intraocular dynamics is essential for safe and effective surgery.¹⁹

Mentorship and Training

Structured mentorship is a cornerstone of surgical education. Novice surgeons typically begin by observing experienced operators—often via an assistant binocular microscope—before progressing to simulator practice and supervised performance of individual surgical steps. Close supervision ensures patient safety and allows for progressive skill acquisition under controlled conditions. Effective mentorship provides not only technical guidance but also emotional

support, patience, and professional role-modelling, contributing to both technical competence and surgeon confidence²⁰ Programs that incorporate structured mentorship have been shown to accelerate proficiency and improve training outcomes.²¹

Progressive Practice and Lifelong Learning

Mastery of phacoemulsification requires deliberate and sustained practice, coupled with an ongoing commitment to learning and adaptation. The steep learning curve demands perseverance from both the trainee and the trainer. Evidence demonstrates that repetitive practice and cumulative surgical experience lead to improved outcomes and a reduction in complication rates.²² Ongoing engagement with evolving surgical techniques, technologies, and evidence-based practices is critical for maintaining and enhancing proficiency throughout a surgeon's career.²³

Planning Phacoemulsification Training

Choosing a training centre: Given the steep learning curve of phacoemulsification, the choice of training centre is critical. Centres with a high surgical volume provide sufficient case exposure for skill acquisition within the limited duration of formal training. Studies report marked improvements in proficiency after the first 80–200 cases, with a significant reduction in complications as experience increases.^{17,24} For most structured training programmes, exposure to at least 25–50 supervised cases—either in part or in full—is recommended to achieve basic competence for independent surgery. Greater cumulative surgical experience has consistently been associated with lower complication rates.^{25,26}

Choosing a trainer: As the proverb states, “A student is not above the teacher, but everyone who is fully trained will be like their teacher”.²⁷ A trainee often reflects their trainer's approach, techniques, and even temperament. Therefore, careful selection of a mentor is essential. Ideally, trainees should seek guidance from surgeons whose

expertise, teaching style, and professional ethos align with their own goals. Exposure to multiple trainers can be advantageous, as it broadens the trainee's understanding of different surgical styles, approaches to complications, and problem-solving strategies.

Learning from Surgical Videos:

In the current era of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), a wealth of high-quality educational material is available online. Many experienced cataract surgeons host dedicated websites or social media platforms that feature step-by-step phacoemulsification videos, including full real-time surgical cases, edited demonstrations of key steps, clips highlighting common complications and their management, and repeated presentations of the same step or complication across different cases and contexts. Repeated and focused viewing of these videos has been shown to enhance conceptual understanding and shorten the learning curve. Notable educational platforms include cataractcoach.com, phacohub.com, and phacomentors.com.

Use of simulators in ophthalmic surgery:

Research indicates that surgical simulation training can improve dexterity, enhance hand-eye coordination and reduce the learning curve and increase safety for novice surgeons. Simulators are however expensive and therefore scarce in the subcontinent. Collaborative endowments would be useful for the establishment of regional training centres.^{28,29,30}

Choice of Patient

At the outset of phacoemulsification training, careful patient selection is essential. Suitable candidates include healthy, cooperative individuals who can tolerate a potentially prolonged procedure and have relatively soft cataracts without complicating ocular comorbidities such as lens subluxation or floppy iris syndrome (for example, in patients taking α -

adrenergic blockers such as tamsulosin). Patients with small palpebral fissures, as well as high myopes with deep anterior chambers or hypermetropes with shallow anterior chambers, are best avoided during the early learning phase because these anatomical variations increase surgical complexity.

Elderly patients with bilateral cataracts and good visual prognosis in both eyes, or those with a previously successful outcome in the fellow eye, represent good choices for trainee surgeons. Eyes with complex pathology or poor prognosis should be reserved for more experienced surgeons for ethical and medicolegal reasons. Early exposure to straightforward cases allows trainees to learn proper techniques, develop confidence, and achieve proficiency before progressing to more challenging scenarios.

Anaesthesia: Local (sub tenon's or peribulbar) or topical anaesthesia is administered to numb the eye and minimize discomfort during the surgery. However, when akinesia as well as analgesia is desired the peribulbar or retrobulbar blocks may be employed. Poor anaesthesia may preclude patient cooperation and cause distress for the trainee during surgery

Preparing for the Procedure

Proper ergonomic preparation is essential for both surgeon comfort and procedural efficiency. The surgeon should be seated comfortably with adequate back support, feet flat on the floor, and the height of the chair, operating table, and microscope appropriately adjusted. The patient is first positioned correctly on the operating couch, after which the microscope should be aligned to provide a clear view in that position, ensuring an adequate range of movement of the objective lens. This alignment allows smooth adjustment of the focal plane from the cornea to the posterior capsule as required during different stages of surgery.

Attention to ergonomics helps reduce fatigue and prevent musculoskeletal strain. The surgeon's

dominant foot should rest securely on the phacoemulsification foot pedal, while the non-dominant foot operates the microscope controls. Stability and balance are crucial, and the surgeon should pause as necessary to maintain comfort during the procedure. Before commencing, the inter-pupillary distance of the microscope should be set accurately, and the surgical field brought into sharp focus. For beginners, a magnification range of **1× to 1.6×** is recommended to ensure clarity without excessive narrowing of the field of view.

Incision Size and Positioning

Phacoemulsification incisions typically range from 2.2 to 3.2 mm, with smaller incisions preferred for improved sealing and reduced postoperative astigmatism. The wound size is determined by the phaco probe and the corresponding keratome. Although the incision must be as small as possible, it should remain large enough to allow smooth passage of the probe without excessive fluid leakage from the anterior chamber.

The position of the incision is selected based on keratometric readings to minimize surgically induced astigmatism. Temporal incisions are generally favoured, as they provide better ergonomics and visualization. For right-handed surgeons, the main incision is usually placed at 10–11 o'clock, while for left-handed surgeons it is placed at 1–2 o'clock, with the dominant hand holding the blade and the non-dominant hand stabilizing the globe. In temporal approaches, the incision may be located at 4 or 8 o'clock in the right eye, and 2 or 4 o'clock in the left eye, depending on surgeon handedness. Importantly, the incision should be slightly off the vertical midline (e.g., 10:30 or 11 o'clock rather than 12 o'clock) to facilitate more relaxed and controlled instrument manoeuvring within the eye.

Wound Construction

Phacoemulsification typically requires both a main incision and a side port for the introduction of auxiliary instruments such as a chopper or bimanual irrigation/aspiration devices. Side ports are ideally directed towards 6 o'clock, ensuring good intraocular control, and a supplementary paracentesis at 30–60 degrees from the main incision may be fashioned for capsulorrhexis. All incisions should be self-sealing to maintain anterior chamber stability.

The most effective incisions are biplanar or triplanar, which optimize watertight closure following surgery. Incisions that are too short increase the risk of iris prolapse, while excessively long incisions can hinder instrument entry and compromise clarity of the surgical field. The detailed architecture of incision design has been comprehensively described by Prof. Degvan.¹⁸

Incision Location

A temporal approach is often preferred because it provides improved access and manoeuvrability, particularly in patients with deep-set eyes or a prominent superior orbital rim. Care must be taken to avoid interference from the speculum notch. The phaco probe should be held comfortably in a pen-like grip, allowing free wrist movement and precise control. While surgical ambidexterity is advantageous, it is usually acquired with time and experience. Side ports are generally placed three clock-hours away from the main incision, with adjustments made according to surgeon handedness to optimize ergonomics and efficiency.

Staining the Anterior Capsule

Staining the anterior capsule enhances visibility and facilitates a safe, controlled capsulorrhexis, especially in eyes with mature or white cataracts. Replacing the anterior chamber fluid with air before injecting trypan blue minimizes dye dilution, ensuring concentrated and effective contact with the anterior capsule. The dye should be washed off promptly after capsule staining,

and the anterior chamber then reformed with viscoelastic. Viscoelastic should be avoided before this step, as it interferes with the direct contact between the dye and the capsule. In patients with lens subluxation, it is often preferable to avoid trypan blue altogether because it is difficult to remove once it has entered the vitreous cavity.

Use of Viscoelastics

Ophthalmic viscosurgical devices (OVDs) serve complementary roles in protecting intraocular structures and maintaining anterior chamber stability. Dispersive viscoelastics, such as chondroitin sulfate-based agents, coat and protect the corneal endothelium, while cohesive viscoelastics, such as sodium hyaluronate, are more effective in maintaining chamber depth and are easier to aspirate. The soft-shell technique, described by Arshinoff, involves introducing a dispersive viscoelastic first to coat the corneal endothelium, followed by a cohesive agent to deepen and stabilize the chamber. This approach is particularly valuable during capsulorrhexis or in the presence of intraoperative complications, as it enhances visualization, maintains chamber stability, and protects the corneal endothelium.¹⁹

Continuous Curvilinear Capsulorrhexis (CCC)

The continuous curvilinear capsulorrhexis (CCC) is a pivotal step in modern phacoemulsification. First described by Neuhann and Gimbel in 1990, it involves creating a circular anterior capsular opening measuring approximately 5–6 mm to provide access to the cataractous lens. Proper sizing and centration of the CCC are essential for surgical success. A CCC that is too small can lead to postoperative capsular phimosis, also known as capsular contraction syndrome, and can complicate subsequent surgical steps. In contrast, an oversized CCC may fail to provide adequate overlap of the intraocular lens (IOL) optic by the capsular rim, leading to suboptimal centration and long-term IOL stability. The CCC is typically initiated with a cystotome or Utrata forceps. The tear is begun as a small flap, then gradually

extended in a controlled circular fashion. The surgeon should grasp near the leading edge of the tear and minimize re-grasping to maintain precision and control. If the tear begins to deviate or becomes irregular, the anterior chamber should be replenished with viscoelastic to flatten the capsule and the tear carefully redirected.^{28,29}

Tips for Improving Capsulorrhexis

Developing proficiency in continuous curvilinear capsulorrhexis (CCC) requires deliberate practice both inside and outside the operating room. One useful approach is to practice outside the surgical setting using improvised materials such as a microwaved tomato, a boiled potato, or the cellophane from an intraocular lens package. Although these models do not replicate the restricted space of the anterior chamber, they are valuable for improving manual dexterity and for developing the fine control needed to create a smooth, continuous circular tear.

Another effective strategy is to perform CCC routinely during Manual Small-Incision Cataract Surgery (MSICS). This approach allows the trainee to acquire the fundamental skills in a more forgiving surgical environment before transitioning to phacoemulsification. Repeated exposure to CCC in MSICS helps build confidence, teaches the management of intraoperative complications, and promotes progressive improvement in technique with each successive case.²¹

Hydrodissection:

Hydrodissection is performed to create a cleavage plane between the lens cortex and the posterior capsule by directing balanced salt solution into the potential space just inside the capsulorrhexis edge. A successful hydrodissection is indicated by the appearance of a fluid wave passing across the posterior capsule. The irrigation cannula should be inserted near the lens equator, and small aliquots of fluid should be injected slowly to avoid excessive pressure on the posterior capsule.

Gentle depression of the cannula tip against the nucleus helps direct the fluid circumferentially, away from the posterior capsule, thereby reducing the risk of capsular blow-out or capsular block syndrome.²²

Hydrodelineation: Hydrodelineation separates the dense nuclear core of the lens from the softer epinuclear shell by injecting fluid into the central lens substance. When performed effectively, a “golden ring” or double-ring sign appears, signifying that the epinucleus remains attached to the capsule while the nucleus is freely mobile within it. Adequate hydrodelineation permits the nucleus to rotate smoothly within the capsular bag and to be dialed through a full 360 degrees.^{22,23} This step is crucial for safe and efficient phacoemulsification, echoing the well-known surgical dictum of the Cataract Coach: *“If it does not spin, you will not win.”*

Phacoemulsification Process:

Phacoemulsification involves the fragmentation and aspiration of the cataractous lens using an ultrasonically vibrating probe. Before beginning, the corneal endothelium should be coated generously with a dispersive viscoelastic, which protects endothelial cells from ultrasound-related trauma and enhances anterior chamber depth for instrument manoeuvrability. Controlled emulsification of the nuclear fragments, combined with careful aspiration, minimizes energy use and reduces intraoperative complications.

Methods of Nucleus Disassembly

A variety of techniques are available for nucleus disassembly during phacoemulsification, each with specific advantages depending on the density of the cataract and the surgeon’s level of experience.

The divide-and-conquer technique, described by Gimbel and Neuhann, involves sculpting two intersecting grooves in the nucleus to form a cross. The grooves must be sculpted sufficiently deep to

propagate the crack across the dense posterior plate, particularly in hard cataracts. The nucleus is then mechanically split into four quadrants using two instruments – typically the phaco probe and a second instrument such as a spatula or chopper – and each quadrant is subsequently emulsified and aspirated separately.³¹

The stop-and-chop method is a mixed technique where a single central groove is created to divide the nucleus into two halves. One half is emulsified while the other half remains in the capsular bag, providing some protection for the posterior capsule. The remaining half is then chopped and emulsified. The blunt angle of the chopper helps shield the posterior capsule during emulsification of the second half, reducing the risk of posterior capsule rupture.³²

The phaco-chop, also known as the quick-chop technique, eliminates the need for sculpted grooves. The phaco probe holds the nucleus securely with high vacuum, and the chopper is used to split the nucleus directly. In the vertical chop approach, the chopper is directed downwards into the nucleus beside the phaco tip, while in the horizontal chop approach, the chopper is placed beneath the capsulorrhexis edge and drawn towards the phaco tip to create the fracture. This manoeuvre is repeated to segment the entire nucleus into several smaller pieces – typically about six fragments – that are then emulsified and aspirated.³³

These disassembly methods allow controlled management of the cataractous lens and can be selected according to the surgeon's expertise, the cataract density, and intraoperative conditions.

Lens Chatter Control: Excessive phaco energy from continuous delivery can cause lens fragments to bounce or “chatter” within the anterior chamber, increasing the risk of endothelial trauma and thermal injury. Chatter is reduced by delivering energy in short, controlled bursts, allowing better fragment follow-through and protecting the corneal endothelium. Once the

nucleus has been safely disassembled and emulsified, the remaining epinucleus can typically be removed with aspiration alone terminating any further delivery of phaco energy to the eye.³⁴

Cortical Cleanup: Tips and Complications

Thorough removal of cortical material is critical for long-term capsular bag clarity and IOL stability. The irrigation–aspiration handpiece is used to remove residual cortex with the aspiration port is placed just beneath the capsulorrhexis edge at the lens equator, and the cortex is gently mobilized by sweeping side-to-side toward the centre before aspiration. Removal should usually begin with the sub-incisional cortex, which can be technically more challenging. Broad sheets of cortex should be grasped to reduce localized traction on the zonules. If the cortex is densely adherent or if aspiration risks capsular tear, it is prudent to leave the resistant material, implant the IOL to provide support, and remove the remaining cortex afterward, either by hydrodissection beneath the IOL or, in experienced hands, by gentle aspiration under the lens.

Common complications encountered at this stage require prompt recognition and careful response. Capsular folds or wrinkles appear when the capsule is inadvertently aspirated. Here, immediately reduce the aspiration power to release it, and reform the AC with viscoelastics. Capsular bag rupture demands calm, deliberate management: irrigation should be maintained to prevent anterior chamber collapse, viscoelastic should be injected to tamponade the area, and the rupture should be assessed. If the tear is small and there is no vitreous prolapse, in-the-bag lens implantation may still be feasible. If implantation into the bag is unsafe, a sulcus-supported lens may be placed, using the anterior capsulorrhexis edge for support. If vitreous prolapse is present and appropriate skills or equipment for alternative fixation (such as iris-claw or scleral-

fixated lenses) are lacking, the chamber should be left aphakic for later secondary implantation.

INTRAOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS AND MANAGEMENT

Phacoemulsification carries risk of complications, especially for trainees. Understanding and managing complications in real-time is essential. A few common complications are discussed below.

Leaking wound: This results from poor tunnel construction. It is difficult to maintain the AC because fluidics in the eye cannot be balanced. If unable to manage this, it may be best to reform the AC and make a better constructed wound at a different location. If the old wound continues to leak, a suture should be placed to close it and the tunnel hydrated at the end of the surgery.

Descemet's Stripping: Blunt knives, poor instrumentation or poor tunnelling techniques can result in peeling off the Descemet's membrane from the stroma. Once this is noticed, avoid further damage or extension of the stripping. Try to complete the surgery without further complications and then reform the AC with air at the end of the procedure. This tamponades the Descemet's onto the stroma and allows for proper healing.

Corneal Endothelial Damage: Results from excessive phaco power or large volumes of fluid running through the eye during the procedure (more than 500mls). Corneal edema eventually ensues. Use dispersive viscoelastics liberally and minimize phaco power during surgery to prevent this. Hypertonic saline is useful post operatively.

Anterior Capsule Tear: Occurs when the capsulorrhexis extends too far, risking the capsular bag. Stop, refill with viscoelastic, and redirect the tear. Use low flow and avoid fluid surges. Cortical washout should be gentle and

carefully done. A trainee would need the assistance of the trainer in these circumstances.

Posterior Capsule Rupture (PCR): This is a serious complication with potential for vitreous prolapse. Halt, and do not come out of the eye suddenly as this would reduce the pressure in the AC, forcing vitreous to prolapse. Instead, maintain chamber depth/pressure by injecting viscoelastic with the second hand, only then can the phaco probe be safely removed from the eye. Perform anterior vitrectomy if needed. Place IOL in the sulcus if posterior support is insufficient. Optic capture within the CCC will improve the optics of the lens while the haptics in the sulcus ensure IOL stability. Keep the phaco tip centred and use low power near the capsule to avoid this.

Zonular Dehiscence: This may be preexisting or can detach during lens manipulation or aspiration, destabilizing the capsular bag. Insert capsular tension ring (CTR) for support if available, use gentle techniques, consider a 3-piece lens instead of a single piece, as the haptics expand more and thus confer more peripheral tension and thus support to the weak zonules, akin to, but not replacing the capsular tension ring.

Suprachoroidal Haemorrhage: though rare, can be devastating. Close incisions with stronger sutures, if necessary, then control pressure with medications, consider drainage if severe.

POSTOPERATIVE CARE AND FOLLOW-UP

Meticulous postoperative care is a key to surgical outcomes. Ensure incisions are well sealed. Seidel test can be performed to verify wound integrity. Ensure that sutures are secure and check for suture-related irritation or discomfort if used. Use of an eye shield or patch is recommended to safeguard the operated eye from inadvertent trauma, dust, or rubbing, especially during sleep or transportation home.

Broad-spectrum antibiotics are prescribed for infection prevention a minimum of 4 times daily in the initial week. Post operative inflammation is controlled by frequent dosing of steroids or antibiotic/steroid combinations (e.g., every 2-4 hours, although some surgeons opt for hourly steroid administration in the immediate postoperative period) and gradually tapering over 6 weeks.

Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) alleviate pain and control inflammation, particularly in cases with pre-existing conditions such as uveitis. These should however be used with caution in asthmatics and patients with gastrointestinal ulcerations. NSAIDs have been shown to reduce or prevent pseudophakic macular oedema.³⁵ Mydriatic/Cycloplegic Drops can relieve pain from ciliary spasm and aid in stabilising the iris in cases of postoperative inflammation.

First Day Post-Surgery: Assess visual acuity, intraocular pressure (IOP), corneal clarity, anterior chamber depth and IOL positioning. It is essential to look for early signs of infection, corneal oedema, or IOP elevations. Educate the patient on correct eye drop administration, the importance of hygiene, and the significance of avoiding activities that increase intraocular pressure (e.g., heavy lifting, straining).

Postoperative Complications:

Shallow or flat anterior chamber may be suggestive of a wound leak. If not severe, cycloplegics can be used to dilate the eye and help reform the AC. Otherwise the patient should be taken back to the theatre to reform the AC and sutures placed as needed.

Posterior capsule opacification (PCO) is a common postoperative complication following cataract surgery, occurring when residual lens epithelial cells proliferate and migrate onto the posterior capsule, causing visual disturbances.

Capsular contraction syndrome, also known as capsular phimosis, involves the excessive fibrosis and contraction of the anterior capsule opening,

potentially leading to IOL decentration or tilt. This can alter the refraction and affect vision. Cystoid macular oedema, or Irvine-Gass syndrome, is characterized by the accumulation of fluid in the macula, resulting in decreased visual acuity. Topical NSAIDs and acetazolamide are thought to improve the outcomes but should be avoided in asthmatics to avoid triggering an attack. Intravitreal anti vascular endothelial growth factors (AntiVEGF) should be used within the first month post op if significant improvement is not achieved with NSAIDs.³⁶

Elevated intraocular pressure and secondary glaucoma may occur due to various factors, including retained viscoelastic material or severe inflammatory responses. These should be strictly monitored and controlled. Intraocular lens dislocation or decentration can cause visual distortions and may require repositioning in the theatre. Retinal complications, such as retinal detachment or tears, although rare, are serious concerns that require prompt attention and treatment to prevent permanent vision loss. Patients with posterior capsule rents are more predisposed.

Pseudophakic bullous keratopathy results from loss of viability of a critical number of corneal endothelial cells such that deturgescence can no longer be maintained, resulting in persistent corneal oedema with formation of bullae. Severe discomfort and poor vision are characteristic. Hypertonic saline is very useful in mild cases. However, vision loss in established cases is often irreversible, requiring corneal transplant. Delayed endophthalmitis is an indolent intraocular infection caused by low-grade infections with organisms like *Cutibacterium acnes* requiring intravitreal antibiotics like vancomycin.^{37,38} These postoperative complications highlight the importance of thorough preoperative assessment, meticulous surgical technique, and diligent postoperative care in cataract surgery.

Visual Rehabilitation and Refractive Outcomes

Glasses Prescription: Refractive stability is generally achieved within 4-6 weeks post-surgery. At this point, prescribe glasses for residual refractive error, if needed, including reading glasses for patients with monofocal IOLs.

Refractive Evaluation: If a toric or multifocal IOL was implanted, assess the refractive outcome and ensure proper IOL alignment.

Visual Acuity Monitoring: Periodically monitor visual acuity to ensure long-term stability and identify any new vision changes that may indicate late complications.

Achieving Target Refraction: A major goal of phacoemulsification is achieving the desired refractive outcome. Evaluate refractive results based on preoperative biometry accuracy, IOL power calculation, surgical technique and patient expectations.

Patient Satisfaction: Assess patient satisfaction during follow-up visits, addressing any unmet expectations or uncorrected refractive errors.

Tips for Trainees

Start Simple: Begin with soft cataracts, moving to denser lenses as skills improve.

Perfect Each Step: Focus on mastering each step before advancing.

Maintain Visualization: Use viscoelastic to keep a clear view of the field.

Control Speed and Power: Start with lower phaco power and aspiration, increasing with skill.

Work with a Mentor: Seek guidance from your trainer at a low threshold to maintain patient safety.

Practice with Simulations: Use simulators to build confidence and familiarity with techniques.

If video recordings are available, watch your videos critically to evaluate yourself and decide on steps to improve upon as you progress in training.

Preoperative meetings to evaluate patients and plan surgeries and anticipate complications is a veritable learning strategy. The trainee is walked

through safe thought processes and plans for the best management outcomes.

Complication reviews with the mentor is also an excellent learning process. The trainee should not see this as a witch-hunt, but as a beneficial opportunity for learning and growth.

Barriers

One of the primary obstacles is the high cost of phacoemulsification machines and consumables, which are often unaffordable for many healthcare facilities in the region.³⁹ Phacoemulsification machines requiring expensive single-use cassettes are poorly suited to this environment. Instead, machines with sterilisable, reusable tubing would significantly reduce the overhead costs and allow more economical service delivery.⁴⁰

Future Directions

Looking forward, the integration of phacoemulsification into routine ophthalmic practice in Sub-Saharan Africa holds promise for significantly reducing the cataract burden. Continued investment in training, infrastructure, and research is vital to overcoming existing barriers and ensuring that more patients benefit from this advanced surgical technique. Moreover, exploring innovative solutions such as mobile eye surgical units and community-based screening programs can further enhance access to cataract surgery in remote and underserved areas.

CONCLUSION

Mastering phacoemulsification requires dedication, structured training, and a commitment to continuous improvement. This paper has outlined key guidance points for trainees, covering preoperative considerations, step-by-step surgical techniques, intraoperative complication management, and postoperative care.

Regular participation in wet labs, simulations, supervised surgeries, and reflective learning

from each case will gradually build the skillset needed for this intricate procedure. Engaging with mentors, seeking feedback, and actively reviewing performance will accelerate the learning curve.

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